

AEROELASTIC STABILITY ENHANCEMENT OF HINGELESS ROTOR SYSTEM USING CONSTRAINED LAYER DAMPING TREATMENT

Do-Hyung Kim, Eun-Hee Ko, Keun-Woong Song, and Joung-Wook Sim

*Rotor System Department, Korea Aerospace Research Institute
45 Eoeun-dong, Youseong-gu, Daejeon, 305-333, Republic of Korea*

SUMMARY: The aeroelastic stability enhancement of composite hingeless rotor system through the structural damping increase has been investigated. In order to increase structural damping of the rotor system, constrained layer damping (CLD) treatment is applied to the composite flexures. The characteristics of viscoelastic damping layer are modelled as imaginary parts of complex moduli. Modal analysis of composite flexures with attached viscoelastic and constraining layers are performed using MSC/NASTRAN, and the effectiveness of CLD treatments are validated through modal test. The composite flexures with CLD are applied to the 4-bladed, 2.13-meter diameter, Froude-scaled, soft in-plane hingeless rotor system. The rotor system is tested in hovering condition and it is shown that in-plane damping is increased by means of CLD treatments.

KEYWORDS: hingeless rotor, viscoelastic material, constrained layer damping, structural damping, aeroelastic stability

INTRODUCTION

Hingeless or bearingless main rotor systems for helicopters offer remarkable simplicity in hub design compared to conventional articulated rotor system, and composite materials are increasingly used in the rotor systems because of their high specific stiffness, specific strength, excellent fatigue characteristics, and so on. Composite structures can be favourably manufactured to have expected static or dynamic behavior through the tailoring of anisotropic characteristic of composite materials.

For hingeless rotor system, the flap and lag hinges are removed and the elastomeric bearings are often adopted for feathering degree of freedom. And the flexures allow flap and lag motion through elastic deformation. Large amount of aerodynamic moments can be transmitted to rotor shaft because of the absence of hinges, accordingly excessive vibration, aeromechanical and aeroelastic instability problems of rotor system can occur. In order to reduce vibration and increase stability, sufficient in-plane (lead-lag mode) damping is required. Conventional helicopters have been equipped with elastomeric or hydraulic lag mode dampers in order to maintain stabilities. However these type of dampers increase complexity of hub system, weight and aerodynamic drag [1]. Therefore practical and effective method is required for the reduction of vibration and guarantee of stability. For this purpose,

active control approaches to minimize vibration and enhance stability have been intensively studied. These efforts include trailing-edge flaps (TEF) with smart actuators [2], and controllable twist blades with embedded piezoelectric actuators [3], stability augmentation system [4], magneto-rheological fluid damper [5], active constrained layer damping [1], and so on. Active methods can be effective at designed operating condition and show excellent performance. However additional equipments and costs are required for the construction of control system, and moreover, performance degradation can take place due to the operating condition variations, and sometimes it can induce instabilities. Compared with active control approach, passive damping enhancement approaches support baseline stability, though it does not give us outstanding performance. Among various passive approaches, the surface damping treatment employing viscoelastic materials, especially constrained layer damping (CLD) treatment is one of the most efficient methods to reduce vibrations in numerous dynamic applications [6].

This paper investigates aeroelastic stability enhancement of a small-scale hingeless rotor system via structural damping increase of composite flexures. For this purpose, CLD treatments are adopted in order to minimize structural changes and maintain simplicity of the hingeless rotor system. Damping characteristic of viscoelastic layer is modeled as imaginary part of complex stiffness. Modal analysis of composite flexures with attached viscoelastic and constraining layers are performed using MSC/NASTRAN, and the effectiveness of CLD treatments are validated through modal test. The composite flexures with CLD are applied to the 4-bladed, 2.13-meter diameter, Froude-scaled, soft in-plane hingeless rotor system. The aeroelastic stability is tested in hovering condition and the effectiveness of CLD treatment is investigated.

DAMPING MODELING AND ANALYSIS

Damping is defined to be the irreversible loss of energy from the structure that occurs through a variety of physical mechanisms. The existence of damping in structures is obvious to anyone who has observed structural vibration amplitudes decay over some finite time period after the source of excitation is removed. Damping of structures can be expressed in various forms as follows:

$$\eta = \psi/2\pi = \tan(\gamma) = 2\zeta = (\omega_2^2 - \omega_1^2)/2\omega_h^2 = 1/Q = \delta/\pi \quad (1)$$

where, η is loss factor, ψ is specific damping capacity, γ is loss angle, ζ is damping ratio, ω_h is natural frequency, ω_1 and ω_2 are frequencies which indicate half power bandwidth, Q is amplification factor, and δ is logarithmic decrement.

Before investigating flexure structures, structural damping analysis of a sandwich cantilever beam with a viscoelastic core has been performed. The frequencies and corresponding modal loss factors from MSC/NASTRAN with complex eigenvalue analysis and finite element analysis based on layerwise displacement theory, which is the same in-house code used in Ref. 6, are compared with a sixth order beam theory solution [7]. In the analyses using FEM and NASTRAN, complex moduli were used for incorporating damping characteristics of viscoelastic layer. The analysis model is presented in Fig. 1 and the results are shown in Table 1. In the FEM analysis, an eight-node isoparametric element, 7×1 mesh size, and 3 subdivisions through the thickness were used, and $49 \times 7 \times 3$ HEX8 elements were used in NASTRAN analysis. The NASTRAN with complex eigenvalue analysis gives us reasonable results.

Fig. 1: Sandwich beam with embedded viscoelastic layer

Table 1: Modal frequencies and loss factors of sandwich beam model

	Ref. 7		LWPT		NASTRAN	
	6th-order D.E.		complex stiffness		complex eigenvalue	
	f (Hz)	η_n^*	f (Hz)	η_n^*	f (Hz)	η_n^*
core loss factor = 0.1						
Mode 1	64.075	0.2815	64.278	0.2799	64.252	0.2808
Mode 2	296.41	0.2424	297.482	0.2426	297.269	0.2422
Mode 3	743.7	0.1540	747.986	0.1546	746.439	0.1538
Mode 4	1393.9	0.0889	1413.08	0.0888	1401.48	0.0882
Mode 5	2261.09	0.0573	2335.59	0.0563	2278.46	0.0563
core loss factor = 0.3						
Mode 1	64.43	0.2723	64.617	0.2709	64.304	0.2803
Mode 2	297.01	0.2399	297.806	0.2409	297.489	0.2418
Mode 3	744.1	0.1538	748.061	0.1545	746.489	0.1537
Mode 4	1394	0.0888	1413.14	0.0887	1401.56	0.0882
Mode 5	2261.24	0.0572	2335.61	0.0563	2278.53	0.0563

* modal loss factor/core loss factor

STRUCTURAL DAMPING ENHANCEMENT OF FLEXURES

Configuration of the hub system is shown in Fig. 2. The principal region of the composite flexure is a square box-beam; accordingly it is not easy to model the flexure using FE code based on plate theory. Hence 3-D finite element analysis using NASTRAN has been applied. For the construction of CLD treatment like Fig. 3, ISD112 (3M) was used as viscoelastic layer and AL1050 was used as constraining layer. Configuration and dimension of composite flexure is presented in Fig. 4 and Table 2.

Fig. 2: Small-scale hingeless hub system

Fig. 3: Constrained layer damping treatment

Fig. 4: Configuration of composite flexure

Table 2: Dimension of composite flexure

Flexure weight	34.5 g
Steel bushing weight	1.0 g
Tip weight (section a)	0.931132 g
Flexure length	151.0 mm
Length of uniform section (section c)	110.0 mm
Width of uniform section (section c)	10.0 mm

In the finite element analysis, sections a, b, and c in Fig. 4 were modeled, and fixed boundary condition was applied at the end of section c. In modal testing, section d was clamped for applying the same boundary condition. The major part of the flexure is section c; the cross-section is square and it has foam core. The lay-up pattern of section c is shown in Fig. 5; 1-ply of [0] UD glass/epoxy (TGN1010, SK chemical) and 6-ply of [± 45] glass-fabric/epoxy (GEP213, SK Chemical) are wrapping around the foam core.

Fig. 5: Lay-up pattern

The vibration and damping characteristics according to CLD length have been investigated. CLD is applied to section c and five cases are considered: 0.0 mm, 27.5 mm, 55.0 mm, 82.5 mm, and 110.0 mm from the right end of section c. Material properties used in the analysis are given in Table 3. Loss factor of viscoelastic material is assumed to be constant: $\eta_{\text{ISD112}} = 0.87$.

Table 3: Material properties

ISD112	$E = 1.76 \text{ MPa}$, $\nu = 0.49$, $\rho = 980 \text{ kg/m}^3$, $t = 0.127 \text{ mm}$
AL1050	$E = 69 \text{ GPa}$, $\nu = 0.33$, $\rho = 2705 \text{ kg/m}^3$, $t = 0.2 \text{ mm}$
TGN1010 [0]	$E_1 = 38.05 \text{ GPa}$, $E_2 = E_3 = 11.78 \text{ GPa}$, $\nu_{12} = 0.321$, $\rho = 1900 \text{ kg/m}^3$, $t = 0.125 \text{ mm}$
GEP213 [± 45]	$E_1 = E_2 = 11.6 \text{ GPa}$, $E_3 = 8.46 \text{ GPa}$, $\nu_{12} = 0.538$, $\rho = 1880 \text{ kg/m}^3$, $t = 0.132 \text{ mm}$
Hard Foam	$E = 54 \text{ MPa}$, $\nu = 0.44$, $\rho = 80 \text{ kg/m}^3$

The experimental setup for modal testing is shown in Fig. 6. Impulsive loading was applied and velocity was measured at the point 10 mm below the free end. Frequencies and loss factors are calculated by polynomial fitting of the measured frequency response functions.

Fig. 6: Modal testing

Table 4: Modal frequencies and loss factors

CLD Length	NASTRAN				NASTRAN			
	f_1 (Hz)	η_1	f_2 (Hz)	η_2	f_1 (Hz)	η_1	f_2 (Hz)	η_2
$\eta_{\text{ISD112}} = 0.87, \eta_{\text{FOAM}} = 0.2, \eta_{\text{TGN1010}} = \eta_{\text{GEP213}} = 0.008$					$\eta_{\text{ISD112}} = 0.87$			
0.0 mm	133.20	0.00873	1277.9	0.00893	133.20	0	1277.8	0
27.5 mm	133.49	0.01221	1279.9	0.01035	133.49	0.00351	1279.9	0.00144
55.0 mm	134.68	0.02564	1272.0	0.01111	134.67	0.01709	1272.0	0.00220
82.5 mm	136.48	0.04067	1259.3	0.01609	136.47	0.03233	1259.2	0.00724
110.0 mm	137.86	0.04862	1265.2	0.03316	137.85	0.04046	1265.1	0.02454
$\eta_{\text{ISD112}} = 0.87, \eta_{\text{FOAM}} = 0.2, \eta_{\text{TGN1010}} = \eta_{\text{GEP213}} = 0.012$					Experiment			
0.0 mm	133.20	0.01272	1277.9	0.01291	133.56	0.00906	1254	0.00932
27.5 mm	133.50	0.01618	1279.9	0.01432	133.40	0.01169	1254	0.01180
55.0 mm	134.68	0.02953	1272.0	0.01508	133.87	0.02220	1246	0.01264
82.5 mm	136.48	0.04446	1259.3	0.02003	135.45	0.03880	1250	0.03120
110.0 mm	137.87	0.05233	1265.2	0.03699	136.71	0.04520	1280	0.03940

(a) first mode

(b) second mode

Fig. 7: Modal loss factor variations according to CLD length

Modal frequencies from NASTRAN analysis are close to experimental results as shown in Table 4. However, it is difficult to predict modal loss factors accurately because exact loss factors of all materials are not available. When the material loss factor for viscoelastic layer only is used in the analysis, analytic loss factors are lower than experimental result. If we assume and use material loss factors for foam core and composite prepreg, more increased modal loss factors can be obtained as shown in Table 4 and Fig. 7. Modal loss factors from NASTRAN and experiments show the same tendency to rise according to CLD length increase. Considering experimental data, the first modal loss factor for CLD = 110.0 mm is five times higher than without CLD, that is, the structural damping is increased by 400 % without significant variation in modal frequency. The effectiveness of CLD treatment can also be observed in frequency response functions and time history as shown in Fig. 8.

Fig. 8: Vibration reduction results in frequency and time domains

AEROELASTIC STABILITY ENHANCEMENT

The structural damping of composite flexure could be increased by CLD treatment as previously described. The next phase is the investigation of the effects of increased structural damping on the aeroelastic stability of the hingeless rotor. Nonrotating and rotating testes were conducted for three cases as shown in Fig. 9; *case 1* is original system, *case 2* is the rotor with single-side CLD treatment, and dual-side CLD condition is *case 3*.

Fig. 9: CLD treatments for rotor system

Nonrotating Tests

Nonrotating modal frequencies and in-plane (lead-lag) damping were evaluated through bench test. With the mast clamped as shown in Fig. 10, in-plane mode was manually excited and the vibration signal of individual blade oscillation was measured using strain gauges at the root of flexures and blades.

Fig. 10: Nonrotating bench test

Fundamental in-plane frequencies and damping obtained from moving block analysis are presented in Table 5, and free decay signals are provided in Fig. 11. Damping ratios for *case 2* and *case 3* are increased by 8.0 % and 31.3 % over *case 1*, respectively. Though increase in frequency occurs due to the stiffening effects of constraining layer, the amount of frequency variation is slight and not remarkable.

Table 5: Nonrotating test result

	Lead-lag frequency	Lead-lag damping
<i>case 1</i>	4.55 Hz	0.0299
<i>case 2</i>	4.68 Hz	0.0323
<i>case 3</i>	4.74 Hz	0.0408

Fig. 11: Free decay signal for nonrotating system

Structural dynamic analysis of nonrotating system incorporating viscoelastic damping layer has not been performed. In-plane damping ratios obtained from nonrotating tests were directly used in the analysis of aeroelastic stability of rotating systems.

Aeroelastic Stability Test and Analysis

The aeroelastic stability test of a rotor system is the investigation of the dynamic response to perturbation; in-plane damping is the object of observation. Strain gauges were constructed in

full-bridge to measure flap, lag and pitch motions. Rotating speed was set to 780 rpm, and cyclic pitch motion was excited through nonrotating swash plate by hydraulic actuator in order to introduce lead-lag motion. In all cases, regressing mode frequency was used as excitation frequency. After a few seconds of excitation, free vibration signal was acquired, and frequency and damping were calculated using moving block method. Aeroelastic stability test were performed at general small-scaled rotor test system (Fig. 12); three cases were tested at several collective pitch angles from -2° to 8° .

Fig. 12: General small-scaled rotor test system

For the aeroelastic stability analysis of the hingeless rotor, commercial rotorcraft analysis code, CAMRAD II (Comprehensive Analytical Model of Rotorcraft Aerodynamic and Dynamic) [8] was used. As previously mentioned, analytic model of the hingeless rotor does not include CLD treatment; the effects of CLD treatment obtained from nonrotating tests are used as in-plane modal damping values in the analysis.

Table 6: Analysis and test results for in-plane mode

collective pitch (degree)	case 1		case 2		case 3	
	f (Hz)	ζ	f (Hz)	ζ	f (Hz)	ζ
CAMRAD II Analysis						
-4	8.023	0.0488	8.022	0.0512	8.018	0.0597
-2	8.039	0.0400	8.038	0.0424	8.035	0.0509
0	8.033	0.0340	8.032	0.0364	8.03	0.0449
2	8.032	0.0327	8.031	0.0351	8.028	0.0435
4	8.026	0.0344	8.025	0.0368	8.023	0.0453
6	8.023	0.0377	8.022	0.0401	8.019	0.0486
8	8.020	0.0418	8.019	0.0442	8.016	0.0528
10	8.012	0.0483	8.011	0.0507	8.008	0.0594
Rotating Test Result						
-2	6.951	0.0280	6.952	0.0301	6.954	0.0333
0	6.969	0.0240	7.010	0.0267	7.010	0.0330
2	6.945	0.0170	7.010	0.0217	7.120	0.0387
6	6.918	0.0220	6.950	0.0260	6.982	0.0309
8	6.893	0.0283	6.924	0.0304	6.871	0.0323

Results from CAMRAD analysis and rotating tests for in-plane mode are presented in Table 6 and Fig. 13. Frequencies and damping of analysis results are higher than test results. Exact

modeling of rotor system is very complicated, and the present analysis model may not represent actual rotor system in detail. However, damping ratios are showing the same tendency to increase as the structural damping of flexure itself increases. In case of analysis, the amounts of damping ratio shifts over all collective pitch angles are almost constant. The experimental result shows an average increase in damping ratio for *case 2* and *case 3* are 0.0031 and 0.0078, respectively. Minimum damping is observed at collective pitch angle = 2°. At this pitch angle, in-plane damping ratios for *case 2* and *case 3* are increased by 27.8 % and 68.5 % over *case 1*, respectively.

Fig. 13: In-plane damping as a function of collective pitch angle at 780 rpm

It can be seen that the in-plane damping of the rotor system in hover is increased by applying CLD treatment; consequently the aeroelastic stability is increased. And the cause of the difference between analysis and test is under investigation.

CONCLUSION

The present study investigates the aeroelastic stability enhancement of composite hingeless rotor system through structural damping increase. The CLD treatment was utilized for increasing the structural damping of composite flexures. The effectiveness of CLD treatment is observed in analysis and experimental results. The first modal loss factor of the flexure is increased by 400 % without significant variation in modal frequency. The CLD treated flexures were applied to the rotor system for the aeroelastic stability enhancement. Nonrotating tests were performed to evaluating the structural damping increase of the rotor system. And rotating tests in hovering have been executed to observe in-plane damping variations as the structural damping changes. The rotating tests results show that the aeroelastic stability of the rotor system is increased by means of CLD treatments. Though CLD approach does not give us excellent performance, it can provide us simple and practical way of damping enhancement without increasing complexity of original system.

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